

ISic0008

Funerary inscription for Vibia Pothine

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

volcanic (pietra lavica locale)

Object

stele

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lipara

Place of origin (modern)

Lipari

Provenance

Exact findspot not known

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Antonino Salinas, inventory 3508

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. D (is) M (anibus)
2. Vibiae Pothine
3. Vibia Euphro
4. syne fil (ia)
5. matri pient (issimae)
6. et Theophanes
7. coniugi
8. merenti

Apparatus

Translation (en)

To the shades of Vibia Pothine. Vibia Euphrosyne for her much lamented
mother and Theophanes for his
deserving wife.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 175715

EDR 076311

EDCS 9400437

PHI 334888

Bibliography

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